

Data Management Plan for "Maritime spatial planning according to international requirements on the Kurzeme coast" project (C4835.ZPD.PI.0049.P1)

Version 1

Description

The primary objective of the applied research proposal is to enhance the digitalisation of maritime spatial planning (MSP), to propose a digital plan along the Kurzeme coast, taking into account the international requirements of the field and future development of marine cadastre, and to work out the specific recommendations for policy makers, planners, industry representatives and geodesy and other science community. Simultaneously, the proposal will lay the foundation for the development of a subsequent application for an applied international research project, with the goal of preparing more elaborated MSP plans by use of virtual reality or/and augmented reality for other parts of Latvian waters, other countries in the Baltic or other sea basins in Europe or beyond.

Here, a description of the data collection will be given, which refers to data of spatial analysis of conflict mapping in the maritime zone of Kurzeme, notes of stakeholder consultations and data for scenario building.

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

Project No

5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/003

"Implementation of consolidation and management changes at Riga Technical University, Liepaja University, Rezekne Academy of Technology, Latvian Maritime Academy and Liepaja Maritime College for the progress towards excellence in higher education, science and innovation" funded by the EU Recovery and Resilience Facility

Researchers

Janis Kaminskis (0000-0001-6345-8084), Ieva Demjanenko (0000-0001-6585-7900), Leila Neimane (orcid:0000-0002-7905-0208), Ļubova Šuļakova (0000-0001-6752-7825), Davis Sika (0009-0009-6413-4642)

Organizations

Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Data Management Plan for "Maritime spatial planning according to international requirements on the Kurzeme coast" project (C4835.ZPD.PI.0049.P1)

Description:

The primary objective of the applied research proposal is to enhance the digitalisation of maritime spatial planning (MSP), to propose a digital plan along the Kurzeme coast, taking into account the international requirements of the field and future development of marine cadastre, and to work out the specific recommendations for policy makers, planners, industry representatives and geodesy and other science community. Simultaneously, the proposal will lay the foundation for the development of a subsequent application for an applied international research project, with the goal of preparing more elaborated MSP plans by use of virtual reality or/and augmented reality for other parts of Latvian waters, other countries in the Baltic or other sea basins in Europe or beyond.

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Organizations:

Riga Technical University

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#) | [EC](#)

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3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2025-01-31

4. Templates

Descriptions

Data of spatial analysis of conflict mapping in the maritime zone of Kurzeme

Data of spatial analysis of conflict mapping in the maritime zone of Kurzeme: 1) identification intersections between incompatible uses, 2) sites where several functions can coexist harmoniously.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The objective is to enhance data accessibility and streamline the research process. The acquired data is examined to fulfill the project objectives.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Machine-readable text
- Observation data
- Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

200

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

Yes

1.1.7 If Yes, please indicate what data set are you re-using?

Zenodo

id: null, Type: null

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Policy-makers and planners, including state institutions and municipalities, as well as industry representatives.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Till the date of publication in a scientific journal.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

GeoPackage (.gpkg), Shapefile (.shp), File Geodatabase (.gdb), PostGIS (database format)

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-01-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

The part of funds are allocated specifically to research data management.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Janis Kaminskis (0000-0001-6345-8084)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Notes of stakeholder consultations

Transcripts from the consultations with stakeholders.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The objective is to enhance data accessibility and streamline the research process. The acquired data is examined to fulfill the project objectives.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

PDF

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

500

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No such data is available from before.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Policy-makers and planners, including state institutions and municipalities, as well as industry representatives.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

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Yes

DOI

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Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

Till the date of publication in a scientific journal.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

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2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

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No

Data for scenario building

Data for scenario building (environmental data, socio-economic data, geospatial data, regulatory and policy data, technological and infrastructure data, scenario-specific data, spatial and temporal dynamics)

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

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No

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Yes

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Zenodo

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